

ENHANCING ABLATIVE RESISTANCE OF CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES VIA INTERLAYER OF SILICONE ELASTOMER MICROPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Thermal protection systems (TPS) are essential for protecting spacecraft and hypersonic vehicles from extreme heat. However, traditional TPS materials such as carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites (CFRPs) require substantial thickness to achieve thermal resistance, leading to increased structural weight. In this study, we propose an enhanced thermal protection strategy by embedding silicone elastomer microparticles as interlayers within CFRP laminates. The microparticles, synthesized via a thixotropic emulsion method using Ecoflex elastomer and sodium alginate solution, are incorporated at 6 vol.% levels in the mid-plane of 10-ply CFRP preforms. Laminates are fabricated via vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) and subjected to oxy-hydrogen flame ablation testing at ~2000 °C. The Si-containing interlayers decompose under high heat to generate silica, forming a thermal barrier that delays carbon fiber degradation. Notably, the ablation resistance increases for composites with PDMS microparticles. These results demonstrate a lightweight yet highly effective approach to improve ablative resistance through in-situ silica formation and suggest the potential of PDMS-based interlayers for next-generation aerospace TPS applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermal protection systems (TPS) are essential in hypersonic and space vehicles to withstand severe aerodynamic heating [1]. Composite materials, particularly carbon fiber-reinforced polymers (CFRPs), are widely used due to their high specific strength and adaptability. For extreme environments where reusable TPS materials such as ceramic and metal matrix composites may fail [2,3], ablative TPSs are employed. These rely on the formation of gaseous boundary layers during decomposition, which insulate against heat flux due to their low thermal conductivity [4,5].

CFRPs typically use the polymer matrix as the sacrificial layer while carbon fibers provide structural reinforcement. Despite their favorable properties, sufficient ablation resistance often requires increased material volume, adding undesirable weight. Various enhancements have been explored, such as particle incorporation [6], surface coatings [7], and resin modifications [8]. Among these, particulate inclusion is attractive due to its processability and minimal impact on mechanical performance. Yet ceramic particles increase composite density, limiting their use in weight-sensitive applications.

Silicone elastomers, with their low density and ability to form protective silica during ablation [9], offer a promising alternative. While prior work has focused on elastomer matrices or coatings [10,11], the use of silicone microparticles as a discrete interlayer within CFRP remains underexplored, partly due to fabrication challenges [12].

Here, we present silicone elastomer microparticles embedded carbon fiber/epoxy laminates (Si-CFRP), as shown in **Figure 1**. The integration of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) microparticles within the matrix of CFRP laminates combines the structural benefits of CFRPs with the thermal protection

advantages of silicone elastomers (Figure 1a). Unlike traditional TPSs, silicone elastomers offer unique thermal protection capabilities. In detail, when exposed to high temperatures, they undergo thermal decomposition releasing silicon-based compounds, thereby forming protective layers of silicon dioxide (silica). This method not only reduces material weight but also significantly enhances thermal resistance, making it highly suitable for aerospace and defense applications. The thermal protection mechanism comprises three steps (Figure 1b). First, silicone elastomer decomposes under high temperatures, releasing silicon-based gases. These gases subsequently react with oxygen to form a silica layer on the composite surface and within fiber interspaces. This silica layer acts as a thermal shield, reducing heat penetration. Lastly, the high melting point of silica ensures sustained thermal protection during prolonged high-temperature exposure.

Figure 1. Overview of preparation and thermal protection mechanism of Si-CFRP. (a) Schematic of manufacturing process of silicone elastomer microparticle embedded carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (Si-CFRP) (b) Ablation mechanism of Si-CFRP with 3-step procedure.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

PDMS microparticles are synthesized using a thixotropic emulsion process with 4 wt.% sodium alginate/DI water medium. Two parts silicone elastomers (Ecoflex 00-30, Smooth-On) are premixed in a 1:1 ratio and stirred at 200 rpm in the sodium alginate/DI water medium to create microparticles. Particles are retrieved after washing process.

Laminated composites are fabricated using vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), embedding 6 vol.% PDMS microparticles in the middle layer of 10-ply carbon fiber preforms infused with an epoxy/amine resin system (INF114, 212). Laminates were cured at 120 °C for 3 hours and machined into 400 mm × 400 mm specimens.

Ablation tests are conducted with an oxy-hydrogen torch at temperatures above 1500 °C. Specimens are exposed to the flame until the complete piercing, and ablation resistance is calculated as the inverse of the linear ablation rate which is calculated as,

$$LAR = t / \tau \quad (1)$$

where t is thickness of specimen and τ is ablation time until the flame pierces the specimen.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 showcase the test-set up for measuring the ablation resistance, and surface morphologies of specimen after ablation. After decomposition of epoxy matrix, carbon fibers of Neat CFRP also decompose immediately due to the high flame temperature (Fig 2a). After the flame pierce the specimen, graphitic region nearby piercing point is identified as the result of the ablation process. In contrast, Si-CFRP resists to thermal attack from the oxyhydrogen flame after decomposition of epoxy matrix (Fig 2b). Furthermore, the generation of white colored debris on the surface of Si-CFRP after ablation procedure is identified. The debris on the surface is presumably assumed as silica, because of presence of the silicon at the chemical structure of PDMS.

Figure 2. Ablation test set up and surface morphologies of Neat CFRP and Si-CFRP after ablation. Ablation test of (a) Neat CFRP and (b) Si-CFRP specimen from 10-ply laminate with and without silicone elastomer particle interlayer (6 vol.%).

Figure 3 presents SEM images comparing the ablated surfaces of Neat CFRP and Si-CFRP. In Neat CFRP (Fig. 3a), fine carbonaceous debris is observed, attributed to the oxidative degradation of carbon fibers. In contrast, the ablated surface of Si-CFRP (Fig. 3b) exhibits the formation of spherical silica particles (~160 nm) on the carbon fiber surface, indicating in-situ generation of thermally protective silica during ablation.

Figure 3. Morphological characteristics of the ablated zone. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of (a) Neat- and (b) Si-CFRP.

Figure 4 indicates that Si-CFRP specimens significantly enhance ablative resistance compared to Neat CFRP laminates. The incorporation of silicone elastomer microparticles facilitate the formation of silica layers on the composite surface, effectively delaying material degradation. Specimens containing 6 vol.% PDMS exhibit an ablation resistance of 129 mm/sec^{-1} , more than double that of Neat CFRP (55.8 mm/sec^{-1}).

Figure 4. Summary of ablation resistance of composite specimen with respect to contents of silicone elastomer particles.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The ablative resistance of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer composites (CFRPs) is enhanced through the incorporation of silicone elastomer, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), as an interlayer of microparticles. The results showed that CFRPs embedded with 6 vol.% silicone elastomer microparticles achieved more than double the ablation resistance of Neat CFRP. These findings confirm the potential of Si-CFRP laminates for demanding aerospace applications where high-performance thermal protection systems (TPS) are desired.

Future work will focus on optimizing the distribution and volume fraction of silicone elastomer microparticles within the laminate structure. Additionally, investigating the bonding properties between PDMS and the CFRP matrix will provide insights into further improving mechanical and thermal performance. These advancements aim to establish Si-CFRP as a versatile solution for next-generation TPS materials.

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